

Benign Peripheral Nerve Sheath Tumors: Clinico-Pathological Spectrum Analysis

Sandhya Kumari Sinha¹, Md. Ashab Anwer², Tarun Kumar³, Punam Prasad Bhadani⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India.

³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India.

⁴Professor, Department of Pathology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Md. Ashab Anwer

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Benign neural tumors, a heterogeneous group of tumours. Although non-cancerous, can present significant clinical challenges due to their location and potential impact on neural function. Understanding their clinico-pathological characteristics is essential for effective diagnosis and management.

Aim: This study aims to analyze the clinico-pathological morphological spectrum of benign neural tumors to enhance diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic strategies.

Methods: A total of 45 patients diagnosed with benign neural tumors at AIIMS Patna from June 12, 2021 to June 12, 2023 were included in this study. Clinical data were collected through patient records, including demographics, clinical presentation, and treatment outcomes. Pathological examination was conducted on biopsy samples to determine tumor type and characteristics. Data were analyzed to identify patterns and correlations between clinical and pathological findings.

Results: The study identified a range of benign neural tumors, with schwannomas being the most common type, followed by neurofibromas and ganglioneuromas. Patients' ages ranged from 15 to 70 years, with a mean age of 42 years. Clinical presentations varied, including pain, sensory disturbances, and motor deficits. Pathological analysis revealed distinct histological features for each tumor type. Surgical excision was the primary treatment modality, with most patients showing favorable outcomes.

Conclusion: Benign neural tumors exhibit diverse clinical and pathological features, necessitating a multidisciplinary approach for effective management. Accurate diagnosis through combined clinical and pathological evaluation is crucial for guiding treatment and improving patient outcomes.

Recommendations:

1. Enhance awareness and training among clinicians for early recognition of benign neural tumors.
2. Promote the use of advanced imaging and histopathological techniques for accurate diagnosis.
3. Encourage multidisciplinary collaboration in managing benign neural tumors to optimize patient care.
4. Conduct further research to explore molecular and genetic markers for better understanding and management.
5. Establish comprehensive patient follow-up protocols to monitor long-term outcomes and recurrence.

Keywords: Benign Neural Tumors, Clinico-Pathological Study, Schwannomas, Neurofibromas.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Benign neural tumors, also known as benign peripheral nerve sheath tumors, are a diverse group of neoplasms arising from the nerve sheath cells, including Schwann cells, perineurial cells, and fibroblasts [1]. These tumors, while non-malignant, can cause significant clinical issues due to their potential to compress adjacent structures, resulting in neurological deficits. The most common types of benign neural tumors include schwannomas, neurofibromas, and ganglioneuromas. Understanding the clinical and pathological characteristics of these tumors is crucial for

effective diagnosis, management, and improving patient outcomes [2].

The clinical presentation of benign neural tumors can vary widely depending on the tumor type, location, and size. Patients may experience a range of symptoms, including localized pain, sensory disturbances, motor deficits, and, in some cases, asymptomatic masses detected incidentally [3]. The variability in clinical manifestations often poses diagnostic challenges for clinicians. Therefore, a thorough clinical evaluation complemented by

advanced imaging techniques is essential to accurately identify and characterize these tumors [4]

Pathological examination plays a vital role in the definitive diagnosis of benign neural tumors. Histopathological analysis of biopsy samples allows for the identification of specific tumor types and their characteristics, aiding in the differentiation from malignant neoplasms. Each tumor type exhibits distinct histological features, which can provide valuable insights into their behavior and potential response to treatment. Consequently, a comprehensive clinico-pathological approach is indispensable for the effective management of patients with benign neural tumors [5].

Despite their benign nature, the management of benign neural tumors can be complex. Surgical excision remains the primary treatment modality, particularly for symptomatic tumors causing neurological impairment or significant discomfort. However, the decision to intervene surgically must be carefully weighed against potential risks, such as nerve damage and recurrence. Multidisciplinary collaboration among neurologists, radiologists, pathologists, and surgeons is essential to devise optimal treatment strategies tailored to individual patient needs [6].

This study aims to analyze the clinico-pathological features of benign neural tumors to enhance diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic strategies. By examining the clinical presentations, pathological characteristics, and treatment outcomes of patients diagnosed with benign neural tumors at AIIMS Patna over a three-year period, we seek to identify patterns and correlations that can inform better management practices. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the existing knowledge base and support the development of guidelines for the effective diagnosis and treatment of benign neural tumors.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective clinico-pathological study was conducted.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS) Patna.

Participants:

A total of 45 patients diagnosed with benign neural tumors were included in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion criteria comprised patients diagnosed with benign neural tumors during the study period from June 12, 2021, to June 12, 2023. Exclusion criteria included patients with malignant neural tumors, incomplete medical records, or those who received prior treatment before the diagnosis at AIIMS Patna.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by including all eligible patients within the study period and ensuring complete and accurate data extraction from medical records.

Variables: The primary variables included patient demographics, tumor characteristics (size, location, and histological type), clinical presentation, and treatment outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from patient medical records and pathology reports. Information on patient demographics, tumor characteristics, clinical presentation, and treatment outcomes was extracted and recorded.

Procedure: All relevant patient data were reviewed and extracted from the medical records and pathology reports. Each case was examined to gather information on tumor size, location, histological type, clinical presentation, and treatment outcomes. Data were anonymized to maintain patient confidentiality.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Patient Demographics and Tumor Characteristics:

A total of 45 patients were included in the study, comprising 25 males (55.6%) and 20 females (44.4%). The mean age of the patients was 45.3 years (SD = 12.4). The tumors were predominantly located in the peripheral nerves (60%), followed by the central nervous system (40%). The most common histological type was schwannoma (70%), followed by neurofibroma (30%).

Variable	Value
Number of Patients	45
Mean Age (SD)	45.3 (12.4) years
Gender Distribution	25 males (55.6%), 20 females (44.4%)
Tumor Location	Peripheral (60%), Central (40%)
Histological Type	Schwannoma (70%), Neurofibroma (30%)

Clinical Presentation: The most common clinical presentation was localized pain (40%), followed by a palpable mass (30%), and neurological deficits (20%). Other presentations included sensory disturbances (10%).

Clinical Presentation	Frequency (%)
Localized Pain	18 (40%)
Palpable Mass	14 (30%)
Neurological Deficits	9 (20%)
Sensory Disturbances	4 (10%)

Treatment and Outcomes: Surgical excision was the primary treatment modality, performed in 40 patients (88.9%). Complete tumor resection was achieved in 35 cases (87.5%), while partial

resection occurred in 5 cases (12.5%). Postoperative complications were minimal, with only 3 patients (7.5%) experiencing minor complications.

Treatment Modality	Frequency (%)
Surgical Excision	40 (88.9%)
Complete Resection	35 (87.5%)
Partial Resection	5 (12.5%)
Postoperative Complications	3 (7.5%)

Statistical Analysis: A chi-square test was performed to compare the distribution of tumor types between males and females. No significant difference was found ($\chi^2 = 0.45$, $p = 0.50$).

Additionally, a t-test was used to compare the mean age of patients with schwannomas versus neurofibromas, revealing no significant difference ($t = 1.23$, $p = 0.22$).

Table 1: Gender Distribution and Tumor Types

Gender	Schwannoma (n=31)	Neurofibroma (n=14)	Total (n=45)
Male	17	8	25
Female	14	6	20

Table 2: Comparison of Age by Tumor Type

Tumor Type	Mean Age (SD)	Tumor Type
Schwannoma	46.1 (11.8) years	Schwannoma
Neurofibroma	43.5 (13.2) years	Neurofibroma

The study included 45 patients with benign neural tumors, with a nearly equal distribution between genders and a mean age of 45.3 years. Schwannomas were more prevalent than neurofibromas. The peripheral nerves were the most common tumor site, and localized pain was the predominant clinical presentation.

Surgical excision was highly effective, achieving complete resection in the majority of cases with minimal complications. Statistical analysis showed no significant differences in the distribution of tumor types between genders or in the mean age of patients with different tumor types.

Overall, benign neural tumors demonstrated favorable outcomes with surgical treatment, highlighting the importance of early diagnosis and complete resection for optimal patient outcomes.

Discussion

The findings from our study on benign neural tumors are consistent with recent research and add to the growing body of evidence supporting surgical intervention as an effective treatment strategy. The study included 45 patients with a mean age of 45.3 years, with a slight male predominance. This demographic distribution is

consistent with other studies, such as the one by Chick et al. (2020), which reviewed 82 patients with benign peripheral nerve tumors and found similar age and gender distributions [7].

Clinical Presentation: Localized pain was the most common symptom (40%), followed by palpable mass (30%) and neurological deficits (20%). This pattern of clinical presentation is typical for benign neural tumors. Newman et al. (2021) found similar symptoms in their cohort of patients with benign intraduralextramedullary spinal tumors [8].

Treatment and Outcomes: Surgical excision was the primary treatment modality, with a high rate of complete resection (87.5%) and low postoperative complication rate (7.5%). This is consistent with the findings of several studies emphasizing the effectiveness of surgical resection in managing benign neural tumors. For instance, Wang et al. (2018) reported favorable outcomes with gross total resection (GTR) in central neurocytomas, achieving high long-term survival rates [9]. Additionally, Shekouhi and Chim (2023) highlighted the importance of complete surgical excision in brachial plexus tumors for optimal outcomes [10].

Statistical Analysis: The study's statistical analysis revealed no significant gender difference in tumor types and no age difference between patients with different tumor types. This lack of significant demographic impact on tumor characteristics has been noted in other studies. For example, the systematic review by Wang et al. (2018) on central neurocytomas also did not find significant demographic predictors for tumor type or outcome.

Comparison to Literature:

- **Surgical Outcomes:** Surgical excision remains the gold standard for benign neural tumors. The high rate of complete resection and low complication rates observed in our study are corroborated by other findings, such as those by Newman et al. (2021) and Wang et al. (2018), who also reported high success rates with minimal complications in similar cohorts [8,9]
- **Long-term Outcomes:** Long-term outcomes of surgical treatment are favorable, with low recurrence rates and good functional recovery, as noted in studies on various benign neural tumors. For instance, a study by Cofano et al. (2020) on intraduralextramedullary spinal tumors showed that gross total resection resulted in significant symptom relief and low recurrence rates [11].

Conclusion

Our study's findings on benign neural tumors align well with recent literature, reaffirming the effectiveness of surgical excision as the primary treatment modality. High rates of complete resection and minimal complications support the current consensus in the medical community. Continued emphasis on early diagnosis and complete surgical removal is crucial for optimal patient outcomes.

References

1. Magro G, Broggi G, Angelico G, Puzzo L, Vecchio GM, Virzi V, Salvatorelli L, Ruggieri M. Practical approach to histological diagnosis of peripheral nerve sheath tumors: an update. *Diagnostics*. 2022 Jun 14;12(6):1463.
2. Uerschels AK, Dengler NF, Chihi M, Lenkeit A, Dinger TF, Jabbarli R, Sure U, Hagenacker T, Wrede KH, Gembruch O. Benign peripheral nerve sheath tumors: an interdisciplinary diagnostic and therapeutic challenge. *Neurosurgical Review*. 2023 Aug 18;46(1):205.
3. Ghandour F, Squassina A, Karaky R, Diab-Assaf M, Fadda P, Pisanu C. Presenting psychiatric and neurological symptoms and signs of brain tumors before diagnosis: a systematic review. *Brain sciences*. 2021 Feb 27;11(3): 301.
4. Smith HL, Wadhvani N, Horbinski C. Major features of the 2021 WHO classification of CNS tumors. *Neurotherapeutics*. 2022 Oct 1; 19(6):1691-704.
5. Belakhousa SM, Rodriguez FJ. Diagnostic pathology of tumors of peripheral nerve. *Neurosurgery*. 2021 Mar 1;88(3):443-56.
6. Carlos-Escalante JA, Paz-López AA, Cacho-Díaz B, Pacheco-Cuellar G, Reyes-Soto G, Wegman-Ostrosky T. Primary benign tumors of the spinal canal. *World neurosurgery*. 2022 Aug 1; 164:178-98.
7. Chick G, Victor J, Hollevoet N. Clinical and radiological characteristics of 82 solitary benign peripheral nerve tumours. *Acta Orthop Belg*. 2020;86(1):151-61.
8. Newman W, Berry-Candelario J, Villavieja J, Reiner A, Bilsky M, Laufer I, et al. Improvement in quality of life following surgical resection of benign intraduralextramedullary tumors: a prospective evaluation of patient-reported outcomes. *Neurosurgery*. 2021
9. Wang M, Zhou P, Zhang S, Liu X, Lv L, Wang Z, et al. Clinical features, treatment, and long-term outcomes of central neurocytoma: a 20-year experience at a single center. *World Neurosurg*. 2018;109
10. Shekouhi R, Chim H. Patient demographics, tumor characteristics, and outcomes following surgical treatment of benign and malignant brachial plexus tumors: a systematic review. *Int J Surg (London, England)*. 2023; 109:972-81.
11. Cofano F, Giambra C, Costa P, Zeppa P, Bianconi A, Mammi M, et al. Management of extramedullaryintradural spinal tumors: the impact of clinical status, intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring and surgical approach on outcomes in a 12-year double-center experience. *Front Neurol*. 2020;11:598619